

Gender equality in 5-to 6-year-old preschoolers' early competences in science do not protect schoolgirls from gender stereotypes.

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Abstract

Science competencies acquired at early years are basic and influence on children's later development. Gender differences in these early science competencies may explain the often-reported gender differences in later science abilities. Research in this field was not usually focused on pre-schoolers. In this study we focus on the interaction between 5-6-year-old pre-schoolers and a researcher while they work on tasks about physics and astronomy in three experiments. Participants were 5-6-year-old children attending preschool in Sevilla (Spain) representing the full range of socioeconomic backgrounds. Over the course of experiments, an increase in the students' number of right answers occurred. Results supported that pre-schoolers' early science competencies are characterized by gender equality and do not explain later-reported gender differences. However, the findings showed that girls are not inclined towards scientific careers, even if they have the same scientific performance as boys.

Keywords: science career; gender stereotypes; preschool; physics; gender equality

Introduction

The concept of gender may change with maturation, however preschool years represent an important period for children's gender development (Maccoby 1999; Perry, Pauletti, and Cooper 2019). As young as two-years-old, children come to understand themselves in relation to others beginning to display gender differentiation (Renno and Shutts 2015; Ruble, Martin, and Berenbaum 2007). Performing the gendered roles previously learnt and observed is essential to children's identity formation (Blaise 2012). However, by two and-a-half years, children's gender construction leads to a rigid differentiation between the genders through gender stereotypes (Mulvey and Killen 2015). Stereotypes were defined as simplified images of the world which help an individual to see the world as more comprehensible than it really is (Holcombe 1922). Individual's behaviour and perception may be affected by stereotypes (Müller and Rothermund 2012). Children begin to develop their own stereotypes restricting their behaviours to a narrow set of gender-typed activities, dress, games, toys, careers, and roles (Blakemore

2003; Miller et al. 2018). In middle childhood these explicit stereotypes decline, although gender stereotypes persist in late childhood and adolescence (Steffens and Jelenec 2011; Wilbourn and Kee 2010; Siyanova-Chanturia et al. 2015). Gender stereotypes are also a social phenomenon. Environment signals to children which activities are appropriate for boys and/or girls (Miller et al. 2018) including games.

Learning by playing means utilizing any kind of play activity as a learning tool, especially in early childhood education practice and research (Nilsson, Ferholt, and Lecusay 2017). However gender stereotypes are present and widespread in children's play (Coyne et al. 2016). In preschool classrooms, a variety of materials such as blocks, dolls, books, or bikes are involved in academically oriented activities with children (Dodge 1988; Granger et al. 2017). Teachers, parents and policymakers should be concerned about children's activities because they can provide different types of learning opportunities (Granger et al. 2017). The development of children's differential cognitive and social skills depends on the nature of activity experiences in early childhood settings and these skills may avoid gender differences in later educational outcomes (Osborne, Simon, and Collins 2003; Oppermann, Brunner, and Anders 2019). Therefore, teachers should facilitate children's involvement in activities that model their behaviours, and logical thinking; providing explanations, commenting on children's behaviour, and asking questions during the activities (Perry, Pauletti, and Cooper 2019; Trawick-Smith and Dziurgot 2011; Keung and Cheung 2019).

On the other hand, STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) concepts should be introduced early in development (Eshach and Fried 2005; Larimore 2020; McClure et al. 2017). The participation of preschoolers in a science inquiry intervention was suggested as one of the factors that can increase their motivation toward science eliminating gender differences and most importantly increasing STEM competences (Patrick, Mantzicopoulos, and Samarapungavan 2009; Günther-Hanssen, Danielsson, and Andersson 2020). On the other hand, previous studies also show the importance of quality science learning situations with regard to children's science outcomes (Oppermann, Brunner, and Anders 2019). Therefore, early science instruction is essential in promoting science interest during childhood (Patrick, Mantzicopoulos, and Samarapungavan 2009; J. V. Whittaker et al. 2020) for later academic success (Morgan et al. 2016) and career choices (DeJarnette 2012; Potvin et al. 2018). Early

STEM instruction can lead to develop positive STEM attitudes in children (Gonzalez and Fryer 2014; Pattison and Dierking 2019). However, research works show disparities in the representation of women STEM fields up to the present (Riegler-Crumb, Peng, and Russo-Tait 2020; Mann and DiPrete 2013; Makarova, Aeschlimann, and Herzog 2019; Mellis et al. 2018). Results from TIMSS (Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study) 2015 (<http://timssandpirls.bc.edu/timss2015/international-results/timss-2015/science/student-achievement/>) have shown the difference in science performance between boys and girls. In Spain, girls scored 6 points lower than boys, much lower than international average 8 points in favour of girls. These differences in scores influence female students' career preferences and increase the gap in salary and block women's access to high responsibility positions (Kunze 2003; Behr and Theune 2018; Arulampalam, Booth, and Bryan 2007; Callaway, Fuller, and Schoenberger 1996; Xu 2016; M.-T. Wang and Degol 2017). Early childhood is a suitable developmental period for interventions designed to reduce the gender gaps in mathematics and science educational and career trajectories (Kurtz-Costes et al. 2008; Master et al. 2017).

Several studies have established that explanations for these gender differences are associated with differences in occupational interests (Su, Rounds, and Armstrong 2009; Lubinski and Benbow 2007; Ehrtmann, Wolter, and Hannover 2019; Price et al. 2019). On the other hand, other studies explored the probability that this gender imbalance in STEM field might originate from gender differences in STEM achievement (O'Dea et al. 2018; Hutchison, Lyons, and Ansari 2019; Cimpian et al. 2016).

A recent study has introduced a model with three factors in order to explain the gender gaps in STEM: masculine cultures, a lack of sufficient early STEM experience, and gender gaps in self-efficacy. Equality between boys and girls in terms of belonging and success in STEM fields should come when women increase their participation from changing masculine cultures and providing students with early STEM experiences (Cheryan et al. 2017). For example, a key strategy to strengthen the idea that women can and should do well in STEM domains could be focus on the many successful female scientists, mathematicians and innovators (McGuire et al. 2020).

Interest is a central predictor of the low number of women entering STEM fields (Su, Rounds, and Armstrong 2009; Wang and Degol 2017). Women switch out of the STEM

majors due to the lack of interest finding other fields to be more interesting. In educational psychology, many studies were concerned about how sex differences in interests develop and how they impact girls' educational and occupational choices (Parsons, Adler, and Meece 1984; Eccles 1994; Sinclair, Nilsson, and Cederskär 2019). Other studies have shown that interest is shaped by environmental factors (e.g., role modelling, parents' expectations, societal values, and educational experiences) (Eccles et al. 1993; Helwig 1998; Bandura et al. 2001; Cheryan et al. 2017). It has been hypothesized that men are more likely than women to enter STEM careers because of endogenous interests (Su, Rounds, and Armstrong 2009; Cardador, Damian, and Wiegand 2020; Blotnicky et al. 2018; Kang et al. 2019). Although social conditions may change the degree to which exogenous interests influence STEM careers, endogenous interests seem to explain why boys are more likely to enter STEM careers than girls (Su, Rounds, and Armstrong 2009; Stoet and Geary 2020).

On the other hand, gender differences in science performance has been broadly researched, but conflicting results were obtained. Some studies have reported small gender differences in favour of either boys or girls (Gibbs 2010; Krinzinger et al. 2012; Robinson and Lubienski 2011; Henderson, Stewart, and Traxler 2019), whereas others studies have not found such gender differences (Hyde et al. 2008; Bakker et al. 2019) with very few studies related to physics. One possible explanation could be that that such gender differences in STEM might emerge from previous differences in scientific competencies arising very early in development. Gender differences in physics have been most reported in late elementary school and adolescence (Häussler and Hoffmann 2002; Hoffmann 2002), and such differences have been observed later in introductory physics in university (Hazari, Tai, and Sadler 2007; Lorenzo, Crouch, and Mazur 2006). There is a growing interest in recent years about teaching of science, and particularly physics, at the preschool level, including gender differences (Dam-o et al. 2018; Z. Wang, Williamson, and Meltzoff 2018). However, studies in the field of mathematics were pioneering at the preschool level (del Río and Strasser 2013; Robinson and Lubienski 2011; Stites and Brown 2019; Zippert et al. 2019). In this study, an extracurricular preschool science experiments were proposed offering a different view on young children's involvement in science.

An important question of when and how gender differences in science achievement arise may be answered examining gender differences at such early years. The aim of this study is to contribute to our understanding of early years academic skills and science gender stereotypes. This study focuses on preschool children, bringing new data to the growing body of research on the STEM gap. An activity focused on astronomy was chosen, since the children were working on these concepts in a teaching unit with their teacher.

Method

Participants

Participants were 20 preschool students (13 girls and 7 boys, ages 5–6) from one Spanish public school located in an urban area (Los Bermejales) of variable socioeconomic status (including middle- and lower-income students) where immigration represents between 19.63 percent of the total population. Average age was 35.44 years old and average income was 11.328 euros below average in Sevilla for the neighbourhood in 2017. School administrators and parents agreed to let the students take part in this study.

Questionnaire

In this study, we have developed a questionnaire in order to investigate students' misconceptions about physics at preschool level. These misconceptions were analysed by means of a questionnaire given to students at the beginning of the proposed experiments (pre-test), and again at the end of them (post-test). The questionnaire consisted of 3 questions taken from different sources: well-established Force Concept Inventory (FCI) for evaluating students' conceptual understanding of introductory mechanics (Halloun et al. 1995), and Astronomy Diagnostic Test (ADT) and Test Of Astronomy Standards (TOAST) for astronomy concepts (Kalkan and Kiroglu 2007; Slater 2014). The questions are shown in Appendix A. These questions were not previously discussed in class. Multiple forms of knowledge representations (animations, diagrams, maps, or graphs) have been frequently incorporated into questionnaires for

item presentation (Mislevy et al. 2010; Mayer et al. 2005). Furthermore, the cognitive load decreases receiving the information by means of verbal and visual channels separately and allows the student to understand the subject better according to the dual coding theory (Mayer 2002) Thus, multimedia environments allow presenting the information in different colour forms and in effective combinations of these forms in all grades of education (Firat 2017; Park, Plass, and Brünken 2014). Particularly, cognitive theory of multimedia learning, dual-coding and cognitive load theory were applied in the literature to design tangible multimedia objects potentially enhancing the learning capability of preschoolers (Tsong, Chong, and Samsudin 2012). There are various studies in the field of assessment in the form of multiple-choice tests revealing the importance of the use of visuals in questions that require a high level of thinking (Haladyna, Downing, and Rodriguez 2002).

On the other hand, social cognitive theory (Bandura 2001) describes human learning and motivation in terms of personal characteristics (e.g., intrinsic motivation), environmental contexts (e.g., school), and behaviour (e.g., career choice). Social cognitive theory was conceived to “explain how people acquire competencies, attitudes, values, styles of behaviour, and how they motivate and regulate their level of functioning” (Donaldson, Berger, and Pezdek 2012). Intrinsic motivation is the inherent satisfaction in learning science by itself (Simpkins, Davis-Kean, and Eccles 2006), and it can potentially influence students to pursue goals such as science-related careers. For this purpose, a 4-point Likert-type smiley face scale was used to measure their motivation because it was easy to administer and score for preschool children easily holding their attention (Krohn 2004; Mulvey and Irvin 2018).

Finally, an item was included in the questionnaire to assess the endorsement of gender stereotypes about science career (physics and astronomy). The careers were chosen based on prior research of the scale of Preschool Occupation, Activity, and Trait–Attitude Measure (POAT–AM), developed as a part of a suite of sex-typing measures including several occupations having gender-stereotypes associated with them (Weisgram, Bigler, and Liben 2010; Liben et al. 2002). Careers with high scores as male or female jobs were included. The items representing each career were linked both to female and male images for which all students can identify (Knupfer 1997; Binns and Branch 1995). Because the objective of this work is scientific careers, images of non-

stereotyped scientists of both sexes were included, and even just an image of a female astronaut as the experiments are framed within the field of astronomy. Further, the images were provided to ensure that all students had a common understanding of each career. Finally, students could make multiple choices between careers.

Procedure

Students were met collectively by their teacher (female) and one (male) experimenter in their regular classroom. Students sat separately to foster concentration and career selection without the influence of other children. Their previous misconceptions were analysed by means of administering to students the developed questionnaire about basic physics and astronomy concepts before experiments were carried out. Teacher explained questions to the students to prevent any misunderstandings (Hill, Thompson, and Williams 1997). The students completed the questionnaire within 30 minutes.

Then, students sat down distributed around the experimenter. Three experiments were carried out in order to demonstrate the concepts present in the questionnaire: one experiment about the trajectory of objects on earth, a second one explaining why the earth does not fall into the sun, and a last one showing why seasons occur. The experiments are based on the results from development research showing that children frequently show good performance in identifying causal interactions and in attending to specific details of motion events (Cohen et al. 1999; Göksun et al. 2013; Harris et al. 2018). The subject of physics includes situations that require both 3D conceptualisation and thinking beyond the earth. ‘Hands-on’ science education involves activities that allow students to discover a scientific phenomenon by touching, manipulating and observing, and placing students in the centre of the learning (Zollman, Rebello, and Hogg 2002; Türk and Kalkan 2018; Gobert 2000). Additionally, there are studies in the literature that indicate that ‘hands-on’ science activities increase students’ attitudes towards science (Kyle Jr 1985; Bristow 2000).

During experiments, the children’s conversations and statements were documented and recorded for later analysis.

Experiment #1

Previous studies revealed that children before 5 years of age focus on one dimension when calculating the direction of the movement of objects, while children from the age of 5 begin thinking in two dimensions (Göksun et al. 2013). A series of experiments revealed that knowledge of gravity does not arise until after 3 years of age (Kim and Spelke 1999). Children's concept of free fall is based on their simple everyday experience with free-falling objects and their intuitive understanding (Harris et al. 2018). Children predict and interpret everyday physical phenomena understanding some basic physical concepts from early life. The tasks used in the latter studies include objects falling after moving horizontally drawing parabolic trajectories in the direction of horizontal motion (Kaiser, Proffitt, and McCloskey 1985; Kim and Spelke 1999; Howe 2017). Research on this issue demonstrates that individuals' physical knowledge was only piecemeal and their predictions and interpretations on physical events were task specific (Mou, Zhu, and Chen 2015; Eckstein and Shemesh 1993). Previous studies confirmed the alleged benefits of physical manipulation in correcting misconceptions about object characteristics that are perceived by touch (Lazonder and Ehrenhard 2014). Then, a simple gravity activity was developed concerning parabolic trajectory. First, every student chose a Styrofoam ball of different radius, held it at shoulder height and dropped it to the floor. The children were asked about what happened when you let go of the ball. Then, experimenter explained that gravity is a force that pulls balls to the centre of the earth, or in even simpler terms, to the ground. Next, children were asked to throw the balls horizontally and observe what happened. They were asked why the balls kept moving forward but at the same time were getting closer to the ground.

Experiment #2

Several interesting demonstrations of circular and planet motion have been described in the literature (Butcher 1987; Makous 2000; J. Whittaker 2008). A simple centripetal force apparatus has been developed in order to demonstrate both centripetal force and satellite motion. First, a Styrofoam ball was used with the goal of introducing students to the motion of free-falling objects. The experimenter held the ball up and asked students what would happen if he dropped it, and all of them answered that it would fall to the ground. He then released it and indeed the ball fell to the ground, explaining that it was due to gravity, as the earth attracts the ball. Then, a Styrofoam ball painted like

earth was attached to a string and the experimenter began to move it in a circle above his head. The experimenter explained that while the earth pulls the ball toward its centre through gravity, the sun also pulls the earth toward its centre through the same force of gravity, acting as the string. Then, the experimenter asked why the ball did not fall to the ground, and several students said because it was attached to a string. However, the experimenter stopped the circular motion and the ball followed a trajectory as in experiment #1, going straight ahead and finally falling to the ground. When he started the movement again, and asked the previous question, students finally answered that it was because of circular motion caused by gravity.

Experiment #3

This experiment demonstrates the different understandings that children have of seasons and the position of earth and sun. Students were not sure how this works but were gaining some understanding as they experiment. This is a complex explanation to learn; extensive research has demonstrated the difficulty students have in acquiring full understanding (Ashcraft 2006; Aubrecht II 2000; Taylor 1998; Plummer and Maynard 2014; Lee 2010), even more so in preschool students. However, previous works determined that students have similar misconceptions at all grade levels (from preschool to high-school and university students) about astronomy concepts, suggesting an inadequate learning environment as the root of the problem (Türk and Kalkan 2018; Trumper 2006; Tao, Oliver, and Venville 2013). For this reason, a hands-on teaching method has been used to help children understand the basic concepts of such a complex phenomenon (Türk and Kalkan 2018; Ward, Sadler, and Shapiro 2007).

A earth-sun model was constructed in order to illustrate the movements of earth, the sun's rays hitting earth at different time of the year, the effect of latitude on energy received from the sun, and the effect of the tilt of the earth. A straw was pushed through the centre of a Styrofoam ball painted like earth representing the axis about which it rotates. The straw was fixed to a plastic cup checking 23.5-degree tilt of the axis. The location of Sevilla city was pinpointed by placing a dot on the globe. Then, a bright lamp was set in the centre of the group in the dark classroom simulating the sun. The earth model was moved slowly around the sun through the different positions corresponding to each season. Students were encouraged to decide at which of the four

positions the city was getting most light and heat from the sun (summer), and when it got least light and heat (winter).

Finally, students completed again the questionnaire after experiments were finished (post-test). Previously, the teacher explained to children one by one the careers shown in the questionnaire.

Results

Analyses were carried out using IBM SPSS v 26.0. A question awards 1 point for a correct answer and 0 points for an incorrect answer. Descriptive statistics of results obtained by gender for each pre-test and post-test question are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of pre-test and post-test questions by gender.

	Trajectory (pre-test)		Trajectory (post-test)		Earth fall (pre-test)		Earth fall (post-test)		Seasons (pre-test)		Seasons (post-test)		Satisfaction	
	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M
Valid	13	7	13	7	13	7	13	7	13	7	13	7	13	7
Mean	0.538	0.429	1.000	0.857	0.154	0.143	1.000	0.857	0.077	0.000	1.000	0.714	2.385	2.429
Standard Deviation	0.519	0.535	0.000	0.378	0.376	0.378	0.000	0.378	0.277	0.000	0.000	0.488	0.870	0.535

Pre-test and post-test percentages of correct responses to questions are shown in Table 2. All results, except pre-test ones, are very similar to those obtained in previous works with older students (Graham 2006; Zeilik and Morris 2003).

Table 2. Pre-test and post-test percentages of correct responses to questions by gender

Gender	Trajectory (pre-test)	Trajectory (post-test)	Earth fall (pre-test)	Earth fall (post-test)	Seasons (pre-test)	Seasons (post-test)	Satisfaction
Male	42.9	85.7	14.3	85.7	0.0	85.7	2.4
Female	53.8	100.0	15.4	100.0	0.0	92.3	2.4

Girls scored apparently better than boys on pre-test (53.8% vs. 42.9%) and post-test (100% vs. 85.7%) for question regarding object trajectory shown in experiment #1.

Most students answered this question indicating the correct trajectory of an object under gravity. Students are likely to correctly perform the pre-test because interactions with free falling objects are ubiquitous in everyday life. Normality test has been carried out previously and data was not normally distributed, therefore, a Mann-Whitney U-test was used. Additionally, given small sample sizes ($n_{\text{boys}} = 7$, $n_{\text{girls}} = 13$, $n_{\text{total}} = 20$) Mann–Whitney U-test was carried out in order to compare by gender. Non-parametric statistics do not assume equal variance and normality in samples, and are usually less powerful than parametric testing (Whitley and Ball 2002). The test result indicates that there was no difference between achievement of boys and girls (see Table 3). Therefore, although there was a difference between boys and girls in correct answers, non-parametric test indicated that there was no gender difference in the question corresponding to first experiment (pre-test and post-test). However, a non-parametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to compare pre-test and post-test performance revealing a statistically significant difference in experiment #1 only for girls (see Table 4). Boys did not improve their scores in questions about object trajectory and gravity force.

Table 3. Mann-Whitney U-test results for pre-test and post-test questions grouping on gender

Question	U
Trajectory (pre-test)	0.699
Trajectory (post-test)	0.643
Earth fall (pre-test)	1.000
Earth fall (post-test)	0.643
Seasons (pre-test)	0.817
Seasons (post-test)	0.311

Regarding question about experiment #2 of circular and planet motion, these were much lower scores than those obtained in experiment #1 (see Table 2). Girls scored apparently better than boys on pre-test (15.4% vs. 14.3%) and post-test (100.0% vs. 85.7%) for question regarding earth circular motion around the sun. Most students answered this question incorrectly in pre-test, probably because it is not a close experience in their daily life. Mann-Whitney U-test result indicates that there was again no difference

between performance of boys and girls (see Table 3). Therefore, non-parametric test indicated that there was no gender difference in the question corresponding to experiment #2 (pre-test and post-test). On the other hand, a non-parametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to compare pre-test and post-test performance revealing a statistically significant difference in experiment #2 for both boys and girls. Students improved in understanding why the earth does not fall towards the sun.

Table 4. Pre-test and post-test Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test for questions by experiment and gender.

	p (Male)	p (Female)
Trajectory (post-test) -Trajectory (pre-test)	0.083	0.014
Earth fall (post-test) - Earth fall (pre-test)	0.025	<0.001
Seasons (post-test) - Seasons (pre-test)	0.025	<0.001

Regarding experiment #3, all students failed obtaining 0% on pre-test both girls and boys. It is very complicated to know correct answer in preschool: tilt of the earth's axis relative to the plane of its orbit around the sun causes seasons. However, 100% of students on pre-test chose that distance between the sun and the earth was the reason for seasons. Most of students (92.3% of girls and 85.7% of boys) chose the correct answer on post-test after experiment #3. Mann-Whitney U-test result on not statistically differences between girls and boys, but Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test showed an impressive improvement on performance for both girls and boys.

To examine whether misconceptions and notions about physics and astronomy could be induced by specific teaching methods or materials, a qualitative analysis of the experiments was carried out. Children's answers to the question about direction of the movement of objects were mostly correct. When shown Styrofoam ball falling, children explained falling using tangible objects and actions, or an unseen force (but they did not call it "gravity"). For example, "You let it go.", "The heaviness pulls it down." and "The Earth pulls it.". Other answers involved things falling because they are not supported: "Ball falls because it is not held". When Styrofoam balls were thrown away, children observed how they kept moving forward but at the same time were getting closer to the ground. Most of the children described perfectly how the ball moved and the trajectory it followed, but as above the description of the causes were diverse: "It moves until it

reaches the ground”, “The ball is stopped by the Earth and no longer moves forward.”, “The ball moves because I've thrown it until it hits the ground.”. This shows that the experiment was very intuitive for children.

Regarding experiment #2 of circular and planet motion, most students answered at the beginning of the intervention incorrectly: the planets were described like “orbiting the Sun at different times.”, or the planets “need heat” to orbit around the Sun. Some of the students gave confused answers, indicating, surely that they did not understand the questions. For instance, one student confused orbits with rings. Another talked about planets moving following a “spiral” orbital path. One student spoke about planets follow each other in a single orbit around the Sun. On the other hand, one child pointed out that “the planets can’t escape because the Sun has a strong pull which pulls”. However, all the children chose a heliocentric model in their comments.

After the experiment, the children's answers became mostly correct. Quite a few of them answered that the Sun’s got a gravitational pull that keeps the planets in orbit around it. And others answered that planets remain in orbit because of the “gravitational pull of the Sun.” Additionally, orbits were described as not being circles by a large majority of the students.

Next, students did not accurately explain changes in temperature patterns across the seasons or the relative position of Earth and Sun at the beginning of experiment #3. For example, a student indicated that “In the summer, more sunlight, the hotter Earth gets”. One child said, “The sun comes out more in the summer and gets hotter”, and other explained “There is a different sun during the summer and winter, sometimes hot and sometimes cool”. The observations suggest that students were aware of a difference in the seasons, but they may not necessarily connect those differences with changes in the Earth’s tilt, which would limit student’s responses to more difficult questions.

Children were exploring and asking questions concerning their understanding during experiment. One student asked, “What would happen to the Earth's seasons if the earth was not tilted?”. During the movement of the ball around the lamp, they pointed out “The light is most direct there, it is getting the most heat”, “So, it is summer in Sevilla”. Children began to reconsider their previous ideas during the educational process rebuilding their knowledge in a significant way. Students recognized the tilt of the

Earth's axis relative to its orbit as the reason for the change of seasons. However, they did not understand that this tilt and the Sun's position in the sky at specific times of the year were connected.

On the other hand, in response to the question "What would you like to be when you grow up?" children provided specific careers or occupations (see Table 5). Before the experiments were carried out (pre-test), a higher proportion of boys provided a police or firefighter career when asked what they wanted to be as an adult (80%). Only 1 boy reported wanting to become a professional athlete such as soccer player (10%). The same was true for the career of chef (10%).

Table 5. Pre-test and post-test jobs selected by children based on gender.

	pre-test		post-test	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
Policeman/woman	5	5	5	5
Firefighter	3	0	3	0
Teacher	0	4	0	5
Soccer player	1	0	1	0
Chef	1	4	1	4
Scientist	0	0	2	0
Astronaut	0	0	1	0
Dancer	0	9	0	9

Of 17 girls who reported their career aspirations, five of them chose to be police officers (23%). As for the rest of the girls, 4 wanted to become a teacher (18%), 4 wanted to become a chef (18%) and 9 wanted to become some type of performer (e.g., 41% dancer). Those results were in accordance with previous studies (Liben et al. 2002; Weisgram, Bigler, and Liben 2010)

Finally, the proportion of boys who said that want to choose a scientific career increased from pre-test to post-test (considering only the occupations of scientists, doctors and astronauts covered by the questionnaire). In the rest of the careers there was no change at all. It should be noted that in the case of girls, none chose a science career, and only teacher career was increased by 1 girl who selected it. Pre-test and post-test percentage of girls and boys selecting science and non-science career is shown in Fig. 1. There was a high gender disparity (30% and 0% for boys and girls, respectively). This is in

accordance with results of previous studies where childhood masculine stereotypes about STEM make girls move away from STEM fields (Dasgupta and Stout 2014; Leibham, Alexander, and Johnson 2013).

Figure 1. Pre-test and post-test percentage of girls and boys selecting STEM and non-STEM career.

Discussion

Large-scale assessments (TIMMS) have reported gender differences in STEM tend to favour boys particularly at primary and high school (Hyde et al. 2008; Stoet and Geary 2020; Cheema 2019). However, several studies showed conflicting findings, some studies reporting mainly a difference in favour of boys (Hazari, Tai, and Sadler 2007; Docktor and Heller 2008; Krinzinger et al. 2012), while others do not report any gender differences in mathematics, (Hutchison, Lyons, and Ansari 2019) (Hutchison et al., 2017), but no studies have been found regarding gender equality in physics. The present study aimed to cover gender differences in physics in young children by focusing on early physical competencies in children as young as 5 years old. This study was carried out because gender differences in science achievement might emerge from differences in science competencies existing very early in development during preschool. The main findings suggested that the hypothesis of gender differences on any of the early key

competences in physics carried out during experiments could be false. Statistical analyses revealed that there was possible evidence for the null hypothesis of gender supporting that boys and girls perform equally well. The observed gender equality is likely to be consistent with earlier results in primary and secondary school children (Acar, Büber, and Tola 2015; Donnelly, MacPhee, and Bates 2012; Lindberg et al. 2010) extending these results to pre-schoolers. Our findings show that at least in the early stages of development, there can be gender equality in physics performance.

The current study was also focused on examining pre-schooler's career choices. Our findings indicate that children generally supported stereotypic career choices, for both boys and girls. The careers chosen consist of several occupations having gender-stereotypes associated from POAT-AM scale, including male jobs such as police officer, firefighter or soccer player, and female jobs such as teacher or dancer (Weisgram, Bigler, and Liben 2010; Liben et al. 2002). Although most children aspired to a stereotypic career dominated by persons of their own gender, 5 girls aspired to a career most associated with persons of the opposite gender (Police officer), but no boys did. This reflects previous research that demonstrates that it is more difficult for boys to engage in traditionally feminine activities than for girls to act in counter-stereotypic ways (Mulvey and Killen 2015; Horn and Sinno 2014).

Previous studies suggested that pre-schoolers tend to hold gender stereotypical beliefs (Bian, Leslie, and Cimpian 2017; Baker, Tisak, and Tisak 2016): only boys may perform practical activities (use tools and fix cars), or only boys are very smart. Those research shows that active and adventuresome careers, typically male dominated, are preferred by boys (i.e. fire fighters, police officers, sports). On the other hand, communal professions such as teaching are female dominated showing girls more interest to participate in (Trice and Rush 1995). Boys are usually stereotyped as instrumental, assertive and dominant; whereas girls are stereotyped as being compassionate, warm and expressive (Care, Deans, and Brown 2007; Croft, Schmader, and Block 2015).

Despite all this, children in this study were perfectly aware of what careers pictures meant, so it is possible that they have been exposed to stereotypical concepts of gender. The usual propagators for these ideas are peers, parents, teachers and the media (e.g.

children's TV talent shows about cooking or singing and dancing) (Heyman and Legare 2004). These sources must be addressed if young children are to be protected from biased beliefs and stereotypes, including reversing the risk of hindering academic achievement and subsequent personal development in life.

As with most studies on gender stereotypes, the present work suffers a lack of generalizability to other socio-cultural contexts. Societal stereotypes continually change, and larger transnational studies should be conducted in pre-schoolers. This is a small-scale study; the findings must not be generalised.

Additional research will be needed to understand the growth of gender differentiation mechanisms in early years, and thus be able to develop different educational interventions. Since this study noticed no gender difference in science achievements as early as ages 4 to 5, future studies should attempt to determine the causes of gender stereotypic behaviours.

On the other hand, it seems relevant that children get a chance to engage in regular science activities. High quality science learning activities are very rare in preschool (Oppermann, Brunner, and Anders 2019; Saçkes et al. 2011). Future research should account for frequency and quality of teachers' science practices regarding child's science interest. Thus, it would be possible to study how teachers' practices predict children's interest in science (Mantzicopoulos, French, and Patrick 2019; Leuchter et al. 2020).

Furthermore, previous works reveal that children's gender is relevant for their science learning experiences (Cheryan et al. 2017; Brandes et al. 2015; DeWitt et al. 2013). Future studies should investigate these gendered patterns associated to teacher's science activities and children's motivation. In this regard, the role of same-sex modeling for the children's interest in scientific careers could not be investigated in the present work, Children's motivational beliefs in science may not only be influenced through teachers' practices, but also by their role models of gender-specific behaviour (Oppermann, Brunner, and Anders 2019). Previous studies show the relation between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs and children's interest was stronger for girls than for boys indicating that confident female teachers appear to be beneficial for girls' motivation in science

(Cheryan et al. 2017). Teachers' self-efficacy counteract the social stereotype of science perceived as male domain. Future research is necessary to explore whether similar mechanisms lie behind the findings of the present work.

The primary limitation to the generalization of these results is small sample size. This is due to researchers were able to gain access to and study a population that was challenging to recruit obtaining ethical and institutional approval. However, as more children join large-scale surveys over the next years, results will gain statistical significance and hopefully demonstrate the beneficial impact on children.

Secondly, the length of the study may be an important factor in determining the effectiveness of hands-on learning through experiments. Post-test and the motivation variable were applied immediately after the educational intervention, assessing short-term learning effects related directly to the experiments. Although previous studies showed that hands-on instruction resulted in relatively lower decrease rates on test scores, there was no possibility of performing a retention test to detect long-term learning success (Ward, Sadler, and Shapiro 2007; Sturm and Bogner 2008; Türk and Kalkan 2018). Experience with hands-on experiments and practical skills of pupils improved during longer educational treatments (Randler and Hulde 2007; Gerstner and Bogner 2010). In future studies, the three experiments can be separated, performed at different times, and carrying out their corresponding post-tests at the end of each intervention. Finally, a retention test at the end of the course, to ensure long-term learning success.

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Appendix A

NAME:
WHAT IS THE TRAJECTORY OF THE BALL?

WHY DOESN'T THE EARTH FALL INTO THE SUN?

WHY DO WE HAVE SEASONS?

DO YOU LIKE THE EXPERIMENTS?

WHAT WOULD YOU LIKE TO BE WHEN YOU GROW UP?

